

Appendix E

Hydroelectric Potential Selected Sites Data Sheet

LIST OF EXHIBITS

<u>EXHIBIT TITLE</u>	<u>EXHIBIT NUMBER</u>
HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - SELECTED SITES MAP	E-1
HTAR-03 - EDH TR-78 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-2-1
HTAR-03 - EDH TR-78 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-2-2
HTAR-07 - RIVIERE BOUILLIE #1 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-3-1
HTAR-07 - RIVIERE BOUILLIE #1 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-3-2
HTAR-11 - RIVIERE DECO - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-4-1
HTAR-11 - RIVIERE DECO - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-4-2
HTAR-22 - RIVIERE MORY - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-5-1
HTAR-22 - RIVIERE MORY - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-5-2
HTAR-24 - RIVIERE TAPION #1 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-6-1
HTAR-24 - RIVIERE TAPION #1 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-6-2
HTAR-26 - RIVIERE RIO BELLE - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-7-1
HTAR-26 - RIVIERE RIO BELLE - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-7-2
HTAR-27 - EDH ART-1 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-8-1
HTAR-27 - EDH ART-1 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-8-2
HTAR-28 - EDH ART-2 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-9-1
HTAR-28 - EDH ART-2 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-9-2
HTCT-04 - EDH GU-1 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-10-1
HTCT-04 - EDH GU-1 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-10-2
HTCT-08 - RIVIERE BOUCAN CARRE #1 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-11-1
HTCT-08 - RIVIERE BOUCAN CARRE #1 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-11-2
HTCT-12 - RIVIERE DE LASCAOBAS - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-12-1
HTCT-12 - RIVIERE DE LASCAOBAS - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-12-2
HTCT-27 - RIVIERE ROCHE BLANCHE - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-13-1
HTCT-27 - RIVIERE ROCHE BLANCHE - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-13-2

HTCT-28 - RIVIERE ROCHE PLATE - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-14-1
HTCT-28 - RIVIERE ROCHE PLATE - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-14-2
HTCT-29 - RIVIERE SAMANA - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-15-1
HTCT-29 - RIVIERE SAMANA - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-15-2
HTCT-31 - RIVIERE LOCIANE - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-16-1
HTCT-31 - RIVIERE LOCIANE - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-16-2
HTGA-01 - GRANDE ANSE #1 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-17-1
HTGA-01 - GRANDE ANSE #1 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-17-2
HTGA-02 - GRANDE ANSE #2 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-18-1
HTGA-02 - GRANDE ANSE #2 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-18-2
HTGA-03 - GRANDE ANSE #3 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-19-1
HTGA-03 - GRANDE ANSE #3 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-19-2
HTGA-04 - GRANDE ANSE #4 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-20-1
HTGA-04 - GRANDE ANSE #4 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-20-2
HTGA-05 - RIVIERE DE LA VOLDROGUE - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-21-1
HTGA-05 - RIVIERE DE LA VOLDROGUE - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-21-2
HTGA-06 - RIVIERE DES ROSEAUX #1 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-22-1
HTGA-06 - RIVIERE DES ROSEAUX #1 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-22-2
HTGA-07 - RIVIERE DES ROSEAUX #2 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-23-1
HTGA-07 - RIVIERE DES ROSEAUX #2 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-23-2
HTGA-08 - RIVIERE DES ROSEAUX #3 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-24-1
HTGA-08 - RIVIERE DES ROSEAUX #3 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-24-2
HTGA-09 - RIVIERE GLACE #1 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-25-1
HTGA-09 - RIVIERE GLACE #1 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-25-2
HTGA-10 - RIVIERE GLACE #2 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-26-1
HTGA-10 - RIVIERE GLACE #2 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-26-2
HTGA-11 - RIVIERE LA GUINAUDEE #1 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-27-1

HTGA-11 - RIVIERE LA GUINAUDEE #1 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-27-2
HTGA-12 - RIVIERE LA GUINAUDEE #2 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-28-1
HTGA-12 - RIVIERE LA GUINAUDEE #2 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-28-2
HTGA-13 - RIVIERE LA GUINAUDEE #3 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-29-1
HTGA-13 - RIVIERE LA GUINAUDEE #3 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-29-2
HTND-02 - PETITE RIVIERE - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-30-1
HTND-02 - PETITE RIVIERE - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-30-2
HTND-03 - RIVIERE BOUYAHA - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-31-1
HTND-03 - RIVIERE BOUYAHA - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-31-2
HTND-05 - RIVIERE DORE - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-32-1
HTND-05 - RIVIERE DORE - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-32-2
HTND-06 - RIVIERE MARMELADE - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-33-1
HTND-06 - RIVIERE MARMELADE - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-33-2
HTND-07 - RIVIERE MORRO #1 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-34-1
HTND-07 - RIVIERE MORRO #1 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-34-2
HTND-08 - RIVIERE MORRO #2 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-35-1
HTND-08 - RIVIERE MORRO #2 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-35-2
HTNE-01 - GRANDE RIVIERE DU NORD #1 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-36-1
HTNE-01 - GRANDE RIVIERE DU NORD #1 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-36-2
HTNE-02 - GRANDE RIVIERE DU NORD #2 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-37-1
HTNE-02 - GRANDE RIVIERE DU NORD #2 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-37-2
HTNE-03 - RIVIERE MARRION - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-38-1
HTNE-03 - RIVIERE MARRION - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-38-2
HTNE-05 - RIVIERE GENS DE NANTES #1 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-39-1
HTNE-05 - RIVIERE GENS DE NANTES #1 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-39-2
HTNO-03 - RIVIERE BON TEMPS - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-40-1
HTNO-03 - RIVIERE BON TEMPS - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-40-2

HTNO-06 - RIVIERE DES BARRES #1 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-41-1
HTNO-06 - RIVIERE DES BARRES #1 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-41-2
HTNO-07 - RIVIERE DES BARRES #2 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-42-1
HTNO-07 - RIVIERE DES BARRES #2 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-42-2
HTNO-14 - RIVIERE DES BARRES #5 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-43-1
HTNO-14 - RIVIERE DES BARRES #5 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-43-2
HTNP-01 - GRANDE RIVIERE DE NIPPES #1 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-44-1
HTNP-01 - GRANDE RIVIERE DE NIPPES #1 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-44-2
HTNP-02 - GRANDE RIVIERE DE NIPPES #2 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-45-1
HTNP-02 - GRANDE RIVIERE DE NIPPES #2 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-45-2
HTNP-04 - RIVIERE DES BARRADERES - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-46-1
HTNP-04 - RIVIERE DES BARRADERES - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-46-2
HTNP-05 - RIVIERE SAUT DU BARIL - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-47-1
HTNP-05 - RIVIERE SAUT DU BARIL - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-47-2
HTOT-02 - RAVINE DONYEN - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-48-1
HTOT-02 - RAVINE DONYEN - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-48-2
HTOT-03 - RAVINE GRANDE - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-49-1
HTOT-03 - RAVINE GRANDE - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-49-2
HTOT-04 - RAVINE MINERVE - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-50-1
HTOT-04 - RAVINE MINERVE - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-50-2
HTOT-07 - RIVIERE AU FOURE (MOMANCE) - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-51-1
HTOT-07 - RIVIERE AU FOURE (MOMANCE) - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-51-2
HTOT-09 - RIVIERE BARRET - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-52-1
HTOT-09 - RIVIERE BARRET - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-52-2
HTOT-10 - RIVIERE BLANCHE OUEST #1 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-53-1
HTOT-10 - RIVIERE BLANCHE OUEST #1 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-53-2
HTOT-11 - RIVIERE BLANCHE OUEST #2 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-54-1

HTOT-11 - RIVIERE BLANCHE OUEST #2 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-54-2
HTOT-12 - RIVIERE BOUCAN GREFFIN - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-55-1
HTOT-12 - RIVIERE BOUCAN GREFFIN - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-55-2
HTOT-13 - RIVIERE CAZALE #1 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-56-1
HTOT-13 - RIVIERE CAZALE #1 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-56-2
HTOT-14 - RIVIERE CAZALE #2 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-57-1
HTOT-14 - RIVIERE CAZALE #2 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-57-2
HTOT-15 - RIVIERE CAZALE #3 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-58-1
HTOT-15 - RIVIERE CAZALE #3 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-58-2
HTOT-17 - RIVIERE FOND PARISIEN #1 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-59-1
HTOT-17 - RIVIERE FOND PARISIEN #1 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-59-2
HTOT-18 - RIVIERE FOND PARISIEN #2 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-60-1
HTOT-18 - RIVIERE FOND PARISIEN #2 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-60-2
HTOT-19 - RIVIERE FROIDE - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-61-1
HTOT-19 - RIVIERE FROIDE - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-61-2
HTOT-20 - RAVINE EAU FATIGUEE - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-62-1
HTOT-20 - RAVINE EAU FATIGUEE - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-62-2
HTOT-23 - RIVIERE MOMANCE #1 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-63-1
HTOT-23 - RIVIERE MOMANCE #1 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-63-2
HTOT-24 - RIVIERE MOMANCE #2 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-64-1
HTOT-24 - RIVIERE MOMANCE #2 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-64-2
HTOT-25 - RIVIERE MOMANCE #3 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-65-1
HTOT-25 - RIVIERE MOMANCE #3 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-65-2
HTOT-27 - RIVIERE REDOUTE - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-66-1
HTOT-27 - RIVIERE REDOUTE - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-66-2
HTOT-30 - RIVIERE GRISE #1 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-67-1
HTOT-30 - RIVIERE GRISE #1 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-67-2

HTOT-31 - RIVIERE GRISE #2 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-68-1
HTOT-31 - RIVIERE GRISE #2 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-68-2
HTOT-32 - RIVIERE GRISE #3 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-69-1
HTOT-32 - RIVIERE GRISE #3 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-69-2
HTSD-01 - RAVINE DU SUD - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-70-1
HTSD-01 - RAVINE DU SUD - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-70-2
HTSD-02 - RIVIERE ACUL - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-71-1
HTSD-02 - RIVIERE ACUL - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-71-2
HTSD-03 - RIVIERE CAVAILLON - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-72-1
HTSD-03 - RIVIERE CAVAILLON - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-72-2
HTSD-05 - RIVIERE COTES DE FER - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-73-1
HTSD-05 - RIVIERE COTES DE FER - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-73-2
HTSD-06 - RIVIERE DES ANGLAIS #1 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-74-1
HTSD-06 - RIVIERE DES ANGLAIS #1 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-74-2
HTSD-07 - RIVIERE DES ANGLAIS #2 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-75-1
HTSD-07 - RIVIERE DES ANGLAIS #2 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-75-2
HTSD-10 - RIVIERE PORT A PIMENT - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-76-1
HTSD-10 - RIVIERE PORT A PIMENT - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-76-2
HTSE-05 - RIVIERE BAINET #1 - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-77-1
HTSE-05 - RIVIERE BAINET #1 - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-77-2
HTSE-11 - RIVIERE JACMEL BRAS DROIT - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-78-1
HTSE-11 - RIVIERE JACMEL BRAS DROIT - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-78-2
HTSE-12 - RIVIERE JACMEL BRAS GAUCHE - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-79-1
HTSE-12 - RIVIERE JACMEL BRAS GAUCHE - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-79-2
HTSE-16 - RIVIERE MADAME LOUIS - SHEET 1 OF 2	E-80-1
HTSE-16 - RIVIERE MADAME LOUIS - SHEET 2 OF 2	E-80-2

SITES CAPACITY DATA					
Site ID	PMAX. (KW)	PAVG. (KW)	PMin. (KW)	ENERGY (KWH)	Class
HTAR-03	1,871	1,617	1,106	14,164,924	Macro
HTAR-07	1,003	700	316	6,127,762	Small
HTAR-11	255	155	62	1,358,092	Mini
HTAR-22	285	163	59	1,429,940	Mini
HTAR-24	342	200	71	1,753,602	Mini
HTAR-26	109	85	50	742,605	Micro
HTAR-27	25,940	17,399	6,413	152,417,346	Large
HTAR-28	40,066	26,932	9,915	235,923,907	Large
HTCT-04	10,358	9,414	7,846	82,463,830	Macro
HTCT-08	213	182	137	1,595,850	Mini
HTCT-12	120	87	49	764,792	Micro
HTCT-27	510	427	235	3,741,517	Mini
HTCT-28	1,337	1,014	587	8,886,734	Macro
HTCT-29	715	588	424	5,153,290	Small
HTCT-31	440	327	146	2,860,795	Mini
HTGA-01	6,099	4,769	2,364	41,776,509	Macro
HTGA-02	4,703	4,025	2,817	35,258,775	Macro
HTGA-03	1,400	1,087	683	9,518,900	Macro
HTGA-04	1,261	1,175	1,028	10,293,385	Macro
HTGA-05	2,664	2,017	1,336	17,672,988	Macro
HTGA-06	4,204	3,301	1,776	28,915,169	Macro
HTGA-07	3,557	2,763	1,527	24,207,545	Macro
HTGA-08	2,484	1,506	847	13,189,180	Macro
HTGA-09	1,482	863	464	7,556,361	Small
HTGA-10	1,448	868	476	7,603,703	Small
HTGA-11	4,070	2,625	1,346	22,992,426	Macro
HTGA-12	2,966	1,924	1,007	16,853,511	Macro
HTGA-13	428	282	148	2,473,342	Mini
HTND-02	514	307	111	2,693,455	Mini
HTND-03	118	76	30	665,268	Micro
HTND-05	502	311	112	2,723,757	Mini
HTND-06	637	388	133	3,399,736	Mini
HTND-07	325	319	298	2,794,131	Mini
HTND-08	228	128	48	1,124,463	Mini
HTNE-01	863	589	198	5,159,936	Small
HTNE-02	1,720	1,167	371	10,221,854	Macro
HTNE-03	184	172	126	1,505,770	Mini
HTNE-05	146	117	53	1,024,318	Mini
HTNO-03	115	66	24	578,227	Micro
HTNO-06	500	291	138	2,552,106	Mini
HTNO-07	105	67	31	587,417	Micro
HTNO-14	321	185	65	1,618,614	Mini
HTNP-01	2,779	2,566	2,263	22,480,002	Macro
HTNP-02	3,268	2,776	2,052	24,318,130	Macro
HTNP-04	91	60	31	523,443	Micro
HTNP-05	175	98	51	857,903	Micro
HTOT-02	592	349	127	3,060,765	Mini
HTOT-03	414	293	177	2,563,015	Mini
HTOT-04	381	271	167	2,375,977	Mini
HTOT-07	467	326	113	2,853,936	Mini
HTOT-09	100	51	20	442,470	Micro
HTOT-10	1,030	815	574	7,136,045	Small
HTOT-11	1,215	960	677	8,407,785	Small
HTOT-12	957	703	461	6,161,945	Small
HTOT-13	483	304	112	2,662,735	Mini
HTOT-14	194	116	41	1,019,885	Mini
HTOT-15	229	134	47	1,174,969	Mini
HTOT-17	1,711	1,268	855	11,105,929	Macro
HTOT-18	345	238	149	2,081,407	Mini
HTOT-19	1,310	809	328	7,090,740	Small
HTOT-20	398	301	191	2,636,379	Mini
HTOT-23	2,977	2,072	771	18,151,407	Macro
HTOT-24	5,179	3,407	1,457	29,849,592	Macro
HTOT-25	827	515	219	4,512,061	Small
HTOT-27	287	191	98	1,671,761	Mini
HTOT-30	2,798	2,189	1,229	19,176,696	Macro
HTOT-31	1,476	1,204	611	10,550,029	Macro
HTOT-32	1,120	994	644	8,710,227	Small
HTSD-01	2,569	1,778	643	15,571,163	Macro
HTSD-02	1,914	1,321	457	11,575,531	Macro
HTSD-03	528	353	130	3,090,235	Mini
HTSD-05	154	153	148	1,342,758	Mini
HTSD-06	1,007	717	289	6,284,839	Small
HTSD-07	1,308	921	372	8,071,174	Small
HTSD-10	916	643	247	5,635,626	Small
HTSE-05	1,841	1,182	383	10,351,643	Macro
HTSE-11	335	270	137	2,363,199	Mini
HTSE-12	747	555	200	4,860,824	Small
HTSE-16	317	160	64	1,405,786	Mini

TOTAL CAPACITY FROM 79 SELECTED SITES
 SELECTED SITES MAXIMUM POTENTIAL POWER 169,047 KW
 SELECTED SITES AVERAGE POTENTIAL POWER 121,741 KW
 SELECTED SITES MINIMUM POTENTIAL POWER 61,508 KW
 TOTAL POTENTIAL ENERGY 1,066,473,842 KWH

LEGEND

Sites Classification

- Pico (P < 50 KW)
- Micro (50 KW < P < 100 KW)
- Mini (100 KW < P < 500 KW)
- Small (500 KW < P < 1000 KW)
- Macro (1000 KW < P < 10000 KW)
- Large (P > 10000 KW)

Cities

- ★ Chef Lieu
- ★ Capital

Roads

Departements

HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL SELECTED SITES MAP

MONTH	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
Flow (CMS)	4.1005	3.9087	2.8848	3.7459	5.1560	6.0919	4.2822	4.7850	6.4639	7.1027	7.9468	5.4904

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS		
PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
WATERSHED AREA	241.09	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	68.45	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
SOIL CAPACITY	287.62	(mm)
PSUB	0.80	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWF	0.28	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.04	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	30.71	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- Selected Site
- Selected Site Watershed
- Selected Site Dam
- Selected Site Reservoir
- Cities
- Capital
- Chef Lieu
- Place
- Roads
- Rivers
- Lakes
- Departements

LOCATION KEY MAP

AVERAGE MONTHLY MODELED POWER POTENTIAL VALUES (UNIT: KW)

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
1,484	1,428	1,106	1,378	1,761	1,754	1,537	1,672	1,754	1,754	1,754	1,828

SITE DESIGN PARAMETERS

SITE ITEMS	VALUES	UNITS/DESCRIPTION
DAM TYPE	1.00	Gravity
DAM HEIGHT	27.00	(m)
RESERVOIR AVERAGE AREA	4.45	(Sq. km)
RESERVOIR STORAGE HEIGHT	9.17	(m)
WATER ELEVATION	270.00	(m)
POWER HOUSE ELEVATION	234.33	(m)
GROSS HEAD	35.67	(m)
PENSTOCK DIAMETER	1.83	(m)
PENSTOCK LENGTH	1,615.00	(m)
CANAL WIDTH	0.00	(m)
CANAL LENGTH	0.00	(m)
NUMBER OF TURBINES	2.00	Francis
DESIGN FLOW	7.20	(cubic meter per second)

SITE CAPACITY (UNITS: KW, KWH)

MAX. POWER	AVG. POWER	MIN. POWER	ANNUAL ENERGY
1,871	1,617	1,106	14,164,924

- LEGEND**
- Selected Site Reservoir
 - Selected Site Dam
 - Selected Site Conduit (Straight Line)
 - Selected Site Station

MONTHLY MODELED AVERAGE FLOW VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
0.8950	0.9115	0.7515	1.4701	2.0120	2.1594	2.0005	2.2028	2.4584	2.4196	1.7412	1.2033

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
WATERSHED AREA	58.11	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	77.94	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
SOIL CAPACITY	224.00	(mm)
PSUB	0.75	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWF	0.33	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.07	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	74.89	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- Selected Site
- Selected Site Watershed
- Selected Site Dam
- Selected Site Reservoir
- Cities
 - ★ Capital
 - ★ Chef Lieu
- Place
- Roads
- Rivers
- Lakes
- Departements

AVERAGE MONTHLY MODELED POWER POTENTIAL VALUES (UNIT: KW)

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
383	391	316	596	820	880	815	898	1,003	1,003	710	537

SITE DESIGN PARAMETERS

SITE ITEMS	VALUES	UNITS/DESCRIPTION
DAM TYPE	1.00	Tyrolean
DAM HEIGHT	2.00	(m)
RESERVOIR AVERAGE AREA	0.00	(Sq. km)
RESERVOIR STORAGE HEIGHT	0.67	(m)
WATER ELEVATION	155.93	(m)
POWER HOUSE ELEVATION	93.85	(m)
GROSS HEAD	62.08	(m)
PENSTOCK DIAMETER	1.22	(m)
PENSTOCK LENGTH	2,257.00	(m)
CANAL WIDTH	2.25	(m)
CANAL LENGTH	1,128.00	(m)
NUMBER OF TURBINES	2.00	Mitchell
DESIGN FLOW	2.40	(cubic meter per second)

SITE CAPACITY (UNITS: KW, KWH)

MAX. POWER	AVG. POWER	MIN. POWER	ANNUAL ENERGY
1,003	700	316	6,127,762

- LEGEND**
- Selected Site Reservoir
 - Selected Site Dam
 - Selected Site Conduit (Straight Line)
 - Selected Site Station

LOCATION KEY MAP

Month	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
Flow (CMS)	0.1125	0.1075	0.0874	0.1695	0.1942	0.2527	0.2160	0.3042	0.3849	0.3900	0.2383	0.1602

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS		
PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
WATERSHED AREA	16.57	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	77.29	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
SOIL CAPACITY	224.00	(mm)
PSUB	0.75	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWF	0.33	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.02	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	21.35	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

- LEGEND**
- Selected Site
 - Selected Site Watershed
 - Selected Site Dam
 - Selected Site Reservoir
 - Cities
 - Capital
 - Chef Lieu
 - Place
 - Roads
 - Rivers
 - Lakes
 - Departements

AVERAGE MONTHLY MODELED POWER POTENTIAL VALUES (UNIT: KW)

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
82	78	62	125	143	183	158	217	255	255	173	118

SITE DESIGN PARAMETERS

SITE ITEMS	VALUES	UNITS/DESCRIPTION
DAM TYPE	1.00	Tyrolean
DAM HEIGHT	2.00	(m)
RESERVOIR AVERAGE AREA	0.00	(Sq. km)
RESERVOIR STORAGE HEIGHT	0.67	(m)
WATER ELEVATION	212.96	(m)
POWER HOUSE ELEVATION	122.52	(m)
GROSS HEAD	90.44	(m)
PENSTOCK DIAMETER	0.61	(m)
PENSTOCK LENGTH	2,680.00	(m)
CANAL WIDTH	1.00	(m)
CANAL LENGTH	1,340.00	(m)
NUMBER OF TURBINES	1.00	Pelton
DESIGN FLOW	0.38	(cubic meter per second)

SITE CAPACITY (UNITS: KW, KWH)

MAX. POWER	AVG. POWER	MIN. POWER	ANNUAL ENERGY
255	155	62	1,358,092

- LEGEND**
- Selected Site Reservoir
 - ⬡ Selected Site Dam
 - Selected Site Conduit (Straight Line)
 - ⊙ Selected Site Station

MONTHLY MODELED AVERAGE FLOW VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
0.0761	0.0712	0.0560	0.1049	0.1212	0.1760	0.1476	0.2192	0.2796	0.2845	0.1681	0.1102

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
WATERSHED AREA	12.57	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	76.77	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
SOIL CAPACITY	224.00	(mm)
PSUB	0.75	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWLF	0.33	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.01	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	16.19	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- Selected Site
- Selected Site Watershed
- Selected Site Dam
- Selected Site Reservoir
- Cities
 - ★ Capital
 - ★ Chef Lieu
- Place
- Roads
- Rivers
- Lakes
- Departements

AVERAGE MONTHLY MODELED POWER POTENTIAL VALUES (UNIT: KW)

MONTH	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
POWER (KW)	83	77	59	116	135	194	164	238	285	285	185	123

SITE DESIGN PARAMETERS

SITE ITEMS	VALUES	UNITS/DESCRIPTION
DAM TYPE	1.00	Tyrolean
DAM HEIGHT	2.00	(m)
RESERVOIR AVERAGE AREA	0.00	(Sq. km)
RESERVOIR STORAGE HEIGHT	0.67	(m)
WATER ELEVATION	243.57	(m)
POWER HOUSE ELEVATION	107.46	(m)
GROSS HEAD	136.11	(m)
PENSTOCK DIAMETER	0.53	(m)
PENSTOCK LENGTH	2,974.00	(m)
CANAL WIDTH	0.75	(m)
CANAL LENGTH	1,487.00	(m)
NUMBER OF TURBINES	1.00	Pelton
DESIGN FLOW	0.27	(cubic meter per second)

SITE CAPACITY (UNITS: KW, KWH)

MAX. POWER	AVG. POWER	MIN. POWER	ANNUAL ENERGY
285	163	59	1,429,940

- LEGEND**
- Selected Site Reservoir
 - Selected Site Dam
 - Selected Site Conduit (Straight Line)
 - Selected Site Station

LOCATION KEY MAP

MONTHLY MODELED AVERAGE FLOW VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

MONTH	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
Flow (CMS)	0.1853	0.1775	0.1395	0.2591	0.3264	0.4097	0.3605	0.4678	0.5684	0.5888	0.3734	0.2556

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
WATERSHED AREA	22.13	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	77.96	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
SOIL CAPACITY	224.00	(mm)
PSUB	0.75	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWF	0.33	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.03	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	28.52	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

- LEGEND**
- Selected Site
 - Selected Site Watershed
 - Selected Site Dam
 - Selected Site Reservoir
 - Cities
 - Capital
 - Chef Lieu
 - Place
 - Roads
 - Rivers
 - Lakes
 - Departements

AVERAGE MONTHLY MODELED POWER POTENTIAL VALUES (UNIT: KW)

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
99	94	71	147	190	244	212	283	342	342	220	144

SITE DESIGN PARAMETERS

SITE ITEMS	VALUES	UNITS/DESCRIPTION
DAM TYPE	1.00	Tyrolean
DAM HEIGHT	2.00	(m)
RESERVOIR AVERAGE AREA	0.00	(Sq. km)
RESERVOIR STORAGE HEIGHT	0.67	(m)
WATER ELEVATION	282.31	(m)
POWER HOUSE ELEVATION	196.34	(m)
GROSS HEAD	85.97	(m)
PENSTOCK DIAMETER	0.76	(m)
PENSTOCK LENGTH	2,663.00	(m)
CANAL WIDTH	1.25	(m)
CANAL LENGTH	1,331.00	(m)
NUMBER OF TURBINES	1.00	Mitchell
DESIGN FLOW	0.56	(cubic meter per second)

SITE CAPACITY (UNITS: KW, KWH)

MAX. POWER	AVG. POWER	MIN. POWER	ANNUAL ENERGY
342	200	71	1,753,602

- LEGEND**
- Selected Site Reservoir
 - ⬡ Selected Site Dam
 - Selected Site Conduit (Straight Line)
 - ⊙ Selected Site Station

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
0.0928	0.0823	0.0644	0.1192	0.3873	0.5285	0.2361	0.3298	0.6485	0.7447	0.2741	0.1446

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
WATERSHED AREA	171.26	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	76.07	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
SOIL CAPACITY	224.00	(mm)
PSUB	0.80	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWF	0.31	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.02	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	0.87	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- Selected Site
- Selected Site Watershed
- Selected Site Dam
- Selected Site Reservoir
- Cities
 - Capital
 - Chef Lieu
- Place
- Roads
- Rivers
- Lakes
- Departements

LOCATION KEY MAP

AVERAGE MONTHLY MODELED POWER POTENTIAL VALUES (UNIT: KW)

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
57	55	50	63	109	109	82	101	109	109	90	68

SITE DESIGN PARAMETERS

SITE ITEMS	VALUES	UNITS/DESCRIPTION
DAM TYPE	1.00	Gravity
DAM HEIGHT	13.00	(m)
RESERVOIR AVERAGE AREA	1.02	(Sq. km)
RESERVOIR STORAGE HEIGHT	4.49	(m)
WATER ELEVATION	350.00	(m)
POWER HOUSE ELEVATION	323.92	(m)
GROSS HEAD	26.08	(m)
PENSTOCK DIAMETER	0.76	(m)
PENSTOCK LENGTH	1,362.00	(m)
CANAL WIDTH	0.00	(m)
CANAL LENGTH	0.00	(m)
NUMBER OF TURBINES	2.00	Kaplan
DESIGN FLOW	0.54	(cubic meter per second)

SITE CAPACITY (UNITS: KW, KWH)

MAX. POWER	AVG. POWER	MIN. POWER	ANNUAL ENERGY
109	85	50	742,605

- LEGEND**
- Selected Site Reservoir
 - Selected Site Dam
 - Selected Site Conduit (Straight Line)
 - Selected Site Station

MONTHLY MODELED AVERAGE FLOW VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
31.8586	34.1069	29.6063	85.9134	168.5927	149.9238	95.4472	140.9287	164.8280	158.9510	82.0802	44.6710

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
WATERSHED AREA	8,507.74	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	72.59	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
SOIL CAPACITY	264.21	(mm)
PSUB	0.79	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWF	0.34	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.16	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	21.29	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- Selected Site
- Selected Site Watershed
- Selected Site Dam
- Selected Site Reservoir
- Cities
- Capital
- Chef Lieu
- Place
- Roads
- Rivers
- Lakes
- Departements

AVERAGE MONTHLY MODELED POWER POTENTIAL VALUES (UNIT: KW)

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
6,849	7,279	6,413	16,037	25,940	25,844	17,594	24,606	25,940	25,940	15,364	9,147

SITE DESIGN PARAMETERS

SITE ITEMS	VALUES	UNITS/DESCRIPTION
DAM TYPE	1.00	Gravity
DAM HEIGHT	20.00	(m)
RESERVOIR AVERAGE AREA	32.87	(Sq. km)
RESERVOIR STORAGE HEIGHT	6.77	(m)
WATER ELEVATION	50.00	(m)
POWER HOUSE ELEVATION	29.72	(m)
GROSS HEAD	20.28	(m)
PENSTOCK DIAMETER	6.71	(m)
PENSTOCK LENGTH	71.00	(m)
CANAL WIDTH	0.00	(m)
CANAL LENGTH	0.00	(m)
NUMBER OF TURBINES	4.00	Kaplan
DESIGN FLOW	159.14	(cubic meter per second)

SITE CAPACITY (UNITS: KW, KWH)

MAX. POWER	AVG. POWER	MIN. POWER	ANNUAL ENERGY
25,940	17,399	6,413	152,417,346

- LEGEND**
- Selected Site Reservoir
 - Selected Site Dam
 - Selected Site Conduit (Straight Line)
 - Selected Site Station

LOCATION KEY MAP

MONTHLY MODELED AVERAGE FLOW VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
30.2605	32.0597	27.7074	79.4588	154.4114	136.8730	86.3427	128.4073	151.6952	147.9604	76.9537	42.3140

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
WATERSHED AREA	8,128.50	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	72.37	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
SOIL CAPACITY	264.38	(mm)
PSUB	0.79	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWF	0.34	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.15	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	20.34	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- Selected Site
- Selected Site Watershed
- Selected Site Dam
- Selected Site Reservoir
- Cities
- Capital
- Chef Lieu
- Place
- Roads
- Rivers
- Lakes
- Departements

AVERAGE MONTHLY MODELED POWER POTENTIAL VALUES (UNIT: KW)

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
10,757	11,345	9,915	24,379	40,066	39,554	26,496	37,148	40,066	40,066	23,597	14,613

SITE DESIGN PARAMETERS

SITE ITEMS	VALUES	UNITS/DESCRIPTION
DAM TYPE	1.00	Gravity
DAM HEIGHT	33.00	(m)
RESERVOIR AVERAGE AREA	21.96	(Sq. km)
RESERVOIR STORAGE HEIGHT	11.16	(m)
WATER ELEVATION	90.00	(m)
POWER HOUSE ELEVATION	56.50	(m)
GROSS HEAD	33.50	(m)
PENSTOCK DIAMETER	6.10	(m)
PENSTOCK LENGTH	46.00	(m)
CANAL WIDTH	0.00	(m)
CANAL LENGTH	0.00	(m)
NUMBER OF TURBINES	3.00	Kaplan
DESIGN FLOW	146.24	(cubic meter per second)

SITE CAPACITY (UNITS: KW, KWH)

MAX. POWER	AVG. POWER	MIN. POWER	ANNUAL ENERGY
40,066	26,932	9,915	235,923,907

- LEGEND**
- Selected Site Reservoir
 - Selected Site Dam
 - Selected Site Conduit (Straight Line)
 - Selected Site Station

MONTHLY MODELED AVERAGE FLOW VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

MONTH	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
VALUES	7.0922	6.5821	4.9218	10.4215	30.9070	34.0908	21.3981	26.4558	38.2650	39.4778	19.0531	10.1160

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
WATERSHED AREA	2,644.68	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	73.58	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
SOIL CAPACITY	282.48	(mm)
PSUB	0.80	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWF	0.34	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.10	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	7.90	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- Selected Site (Orange circle)
- Selected Site Watershed (Yellow outline)
- Selected Site Dam (Orange square)
- Selected Site Reservoir (Blue square)
- Cities (Red star)
- Capital (Red star with dot)
- Chef Lieu (Red star)
- Place (Grey circle)
- Roads (Red line)
- Rivers (Blue line)
- Lakes (Blue area)
- Departements (Yellow outline)

AVERAGE MONTHLY MODELED POWER POTENTIAL VALUES (UNIT: KW)

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
8,660	8,474	7,846	9,766	9,751	9,751	9,751	9,751	9,751	9,751	9,751	9,675

SITE DESIGN PARAMETERS

SITE ITEMS	VALUES	UNITS/DESCRIPTION
DAM TYPE	1.00	Gravity
DAM HEIGHT	42.00	(m)
RESERVOIR AVERAGE AREA	30.97	(Sq. km)
RESERVOIR STORAGE HEIGHT	14.15	(m)
WATER ELEVATION	220.00	(m)
POWER HOUSE ELEVATION	176.02	(m)
GROSS HEAD	43.98	(m)
PENSTOCK DIAMETER	3.05	(m)
PENSTOCK LENGTH	1,137.00	(m)
CANAL WIDTH	0.00	(m)
CANAL LENGTH	0.00	(m)
NUMBER OF TURBINES	2.00	Francis
DESIGN FLOW	31.46	(cubic meter per second)

SITE CAPACITY (UNITS: KW, KWH)

MAX. POWER	AVG. POWER	MIN. POWER	ANNUAL ENERGY
10,358	9,414	7,846	82,463,830

- LEGEND**
- Selected Site Reservoir
 - Selected Site Dam
 - Selected Site Conduit (Straight Line)
 - Selected Site Station

MONTHLY MODELED AVERAGE FLOW VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
0.1890	0.1483	0.0984	0.1790	0.2546	0.6059	0.3624	0.7454	1.2231	1.2589	0.6149	0.3316

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
WATERSHED AREA	73.73	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	75.17	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
SOIL CAPACITY	226.28	(mm)
PSUB	0.80	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWF	0.35	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.01	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	0.37	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- Selected Site
- Selected Site Watershed
- Selected Site Dam
- Selected Site Reservoir
- Cities
 - ★ Capital
 - ★ Chef Lieu
- Place
- Roads
- Rivers
- Lakes
- Departements

AVERAGE MONTHLY MODELED POWER POTENTIAL VALUES (UNIT: KW)

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
158	149	137	156	173	200	194	200	200	200	200	188

SITE DESIGN PARAMETERS

SITE ITEMS	VALUES	UNITS/DESCRIPTION
DAM TYPE	1.00	Gravity
DAM HEIGHT	28.00	(m)
RESERVOIR AVERAGE AREA	1.74	(Sq. km)
RESERVOIR STORAGE HEIGHT	9.50	(m)
WATER ELEVATION	220.00	(m)
POWER HOUSE ELEVATION	192.82	(m)
GROSS HEAD	27.18	(m)
PENSTOCK DIAMETER	0.61	(m)
PENSTOCK LENGTH	155.00	(m)
CANAL WIDTH	0.00	(m)
CANAL LENGTH	0.00	(m)
NUMBER OF TURBINES	2.00	Francis
DESIGN FLOW	1.10	(cubic meter per second)

SITE CAPACITY (UNITS: KW, KWH)

MAX. POWER	AVG. POWER	MIN. POWER	ANNUAL ENERGY
213	182	137	1,595,850

- LEGEND**
- Selected Site Reservoir
 - Selected Site Dam
 - Selected Site Conduit (Straight Line)
 - Selected Site Station

MONTHLY MODELED AVERAGE FLOW VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
0.0630	0.0630	0.0579	0.1148	0.1205	0.1115	0.0968	0.1204	0.1477	0.1640	0.1228	0.0848

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
WATERSHED AREA	7.97	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	69.53	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
SOIL CAPACITY	224.00	(mm)
PSUB	0.70	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWF	0.30	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.02	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	34.42	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

- LEGEND**
- Selected Site
 - Selected Site Watershed
 - Selected Site Dam
 - Selected Site Reservoir
 - Cities
 - Capital
 - Chef Lieu
 - Place
 - Roads
 - Rivers
 - Lakes
 - Departements

AVERAGE MONTHLY MODELED POWER POTENTIAL VALUES (UNIT: KW)

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
54	54	49	96	101	93	82	100	118	120	102	72

SITE DESIGN PARAMETERS

SITE ITEMS	VALUES	UNITS/DESCRIPTION
DAM TYPE	1.00	Tyrolean
DAM HEIGHT	2.00	(m)
RESERVOIR AVERAGE AREA	0.00	(Sq. km)
RESERVOIR STORAGE HEIGHT	0.67	(m)
WATER ELEVATION	434.04	(m)
POWER HOUSE ELEVATION	330.13	(m)
GROSS HEAD	103.91	(m)
PENSTOCK DIAMETER	0.38	(m)
PENSTOCK LENGTH	1,154.00	(m)
CANAL WIDTH	0.75	(m)
CANAL LENGTH	577.00	(m)
NUMBER OF TURBINES	1.00	Pelton
DESIGN FLOW	0.15	(cubic meter per second)

SITE CAPACITY (UNITS: KW, KWH)

MAX. POWER	AVG. POWER	MIN. POWER	ANNUAL ENERGY
120	87	49	764,792

- LEGEND**
- Selected Site Reservoir
 - Selected Site Dam
 - Selected Site Conduit (Straight Line)
 - Selected Site Station

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
0.3355	0.3427	0.3269	0.6571	0.6992	0.6379	0.5467	0.6868	0.7547	0.7751	0.6556	0.4496

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
WATERSHED AREA	19.67	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	68.41	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
SOIL CAPACITY	224.00	(mm)
PSUB	0.70	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWFL	0.30	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.04	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	85.00	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- Selected Site
- Selected Site Watershed
- Selected Site Dam
- Selected Site Reservoir
- Cities
 - Capital
 - Chef Lieu
- Place
- Roads
- Rivers
- Lakes
- Departements

AVERAGE MONTHLY MODELED POWER POTENTIAL VALUES (UNIT: KW)

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
244	251	235	502	510	496	443	509	510	510	501	356

SITE DESIGN PARAMETERS

SITE ITEMS	VALUES	UNITS/DESCRIPTION
DAM TYPE	1.00	Tyrolean
DAM HEIGHT	2.00	(m)
RESERVOIR AVERAGE AREA	0.00	(Sq. km)
RESERVOIR STORAGE HEIGHT	0.67	(m)
WATER ELEVATION	398.06	(m)
POWER HOUSE ELEVATION	299.24	(m)
GROSS HEAD	98.82	(m)
PENSTOCK DIAMETER	0.76	(m)
PENSTOCK LENGTH	2,322.00	(m)
CANAL WIDTH	1.25	(m)
CANAL LENGTH	1,161.00	(m)
NUMBER OF TURBINES	1.00	Francis
DESIGN FLOW	0.69	(cubic meter per second)

SITE CAPACITY (UNITS: KW, KWH)

MAX. POWER	AVG. POWER	MIN. POWER	ANNUAL ENERGY
510	427	235	3,741,517

- LEGEND**
- Selected Site Reservoir
 - Selected Site Dam
 - Selected Site Conduit (Straight Line)
 - Selected Site Station

MONTHLY MODELED AVERAGE FLOW VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
0.1370	0.1381	0.1233	0.2512	0.2602	0.2259	0.1992	0.2569	0.3049	0.3286	0.2649	0.1843

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
WATERSHED AREA	11.75	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	69.05	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
SOIL CAPACITY	224.00	(mm)
PSUB	0.70	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWF	0.30	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.03	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	50.77	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

- LEGEND**
- Selected Site
 - Selected Site Watershed
 - Selected Site Dam
 - Selected Site Reservoir
 - Cities
 - Capital
 - Chef Lieu
 - Place
 - Roads
 - Rivers
 - Lakes
 - Departements

AVERAGE MONTHLY MODELED POWER POTENTIAL VALUES (UNIT: KW)

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
653	658	587	1,150	1,184	1,047	931	1,172	1,321	1,337	1,200	867

SITE DESIGN PARAMETERS

SITE ITEMS	VALUES	UNITS/DESCRIPTION
DAM TYPE	1.00	Tyrolean
DAM HEIGHT	2.00	(m)
RESERVOIR AVERAGE AREA	0.00	(Sq. km)
RESERVOIR STORAGE HEIGHT	0.67	(m)
WATER ELEVATION	921.89	(m)
POWER HOUSE ELEVATION	339.86	(m)
GROSS HEAD	582.03	(m)
PENSTOCK DIAMETER	0.38	(m)
PENSTOCK LENGTH	2,317.00	(m)
CANAL WIDTH	0.75	(m)
CANAL LENGTH	1,158.00	(m)
NUMBER OF TURBINES	1.00	Pelton
DESIGN FLOW	0.31	(cubic meter per second)

SITE CAPACITY (UNITS: KW, KWH)

MAX. POWER	AVG. POWER	MIN. POWER	ANNUAL ENERGY
1,337	1,014	587	8,886,734

- LEGEND**
- Selected Site Reservoir
 - Selected Site Dam
 - Selected Site Conduit (Straight Line)
 - Selected Site Station

